

IMPROVEMENT OF SCHOOLCHILDREN'S SPEECH SKILLS WITH SONGS ACCORDING TO THEIR AGE

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Summary,

Education in the primary grades is associated with a complex and multifaceted theoretical process of developing the professional and personal abilities of students. The main focus of the work of a primary school teacher is a comprehensive study of the characteristics of the organization: taking into account the ways of teaching students of different characters, abilities, stages of preparation and age characteristics. We come to the conclusion that at each particular childhood, the speech development of the child is not established by one specific leading activity, while from the point of view of personality formation, each age period is characterized by "an activity-mediated type of interaction that is formed between the child and the group." And based on the above arguments, we tried to implement them with the help of children's songs.

Key words: *children's songs, age characteristics, speech skills, aesthetic education, teamwork, emotional impact.*

There are periods of human development, and their number is constantly increasing. Physical, biological, speech, psychological aspects of the development of the child are important components of pedagogical periodization, covering the life and development of the student. The environment in which a child is brought up is an equally important factor. The development of speech should be organized in accordance with the stages of development and education should be consistent and timely. Taking into account age characteristics is still the main pedagogical

principle that determines the choice of forms and methods of educational work, as well as helping to determine the teaching load, correctly select and arrange educational subjects, plan the daily routine, work and rest schedule.

Primary school age is a very important period of school age, which determines the development of the intellect and personality, the desire to learn and learnability, self-confidence [5]. The transition to school age is a serious step in the lives of children, associated with large-scale changes in their activities, building new relationships with the school staff, classmates, and performing diverse student duties. During this period, children form the foundations of theoretical consciousness, thinking, speech skills, so the leading activity at this stage is the child's education, which continues throughout the entire school period.[12]

In the transition from preschool to school age, the child changes a lot and becomes more difficult to discipline than before, this is a kind of transitional period [6]. The development of cognitive processes in children of primary school age is based on two driving forces: cognition and feeling. Ushinsky drew the attention of teachers to the peculiarities of the thinking of younger schoolchildren, which develops from emotional-figurative thinking to abstract-logical thinking: the child thinks in forms, colors, sounds, sensations, therefore, pedagogical science should rely on these features of children's thinking [7].

It is very important to know the characteristics of the cognitive activity of students, the properties of their memory, speech, inclinations and interests, as well as the predisposition to a more successful study of certain subjects. Taking into account these features, an individual approach to students in learning is carried out: the stronger ones need additional classes in order to develop their intellectual abilities more intensively: the weakest students need to be provided with individual assistance, develop their memory, speech, intelligence, cognitive activity. Much attention must be paid to the study of the sensory-emotional sphere

of students and to identify in a timely manner those who are characterized by increased aggression, react negatively to comments, and are not able to maintain friendly relations with classmates. It is desirable for such students to introduce a calm classical melody into their "diet", in addition to children's songs, which develop each student's individual abilities for the development of speech. [15]

At the first stage, the main condition for the development of literate speech is the application of the principle of forming and maintaining a stable motivation for learning, using various children's songs in the educational process. In the context of aesthetic education, this difficult task can be solved by instilling in younger students the need for self-expression in music, which calls for constant self-improvement.

An important factor determining the success of speech development is the maintenance of a special emotional and psychological atmosphere in the classroom, which contributes to the optimal assimilation of educational material. Averin points to the fundamental role of such emotions as interest and joy, which are directly and "most closely related to the cognitive activity of the child. Mental success is impossible without the intense experience of these emotions by the child" [8]. With positive emotions, as a rule, any actions are accompanied by interest. Listening to and repeating children's songs introduced positive emotions to schoolchildren in the learning process" [8].

Pupils of primary school age do not have abstract thinking, unenriched oral speech and have limited abilities for analysis, logical conclusions due to age characteristics, so the child enters school with a relatively weak intellect and more developed functions of perception and memory. Teachers use a variety of educational technologies, original forms of education (children's songs), which allow them to quickly immerse children in an imaginary space in the classroom. Auditory memory predominates in primary school students, therefore, for better

assimilation and memorization, it is especially important to develop students' abilities to analyze and comprehend educational material. [3]

In this area, we work with young talents - giving theoretical knowledge and training speech skills, we influence children's senses, trying to evoke emotional experiences in children with the help of children's songs. In this regard, the organization of complex integrated classes with the introduction of various children's songs into everyday life is very useful. Working on the development of speech skills, it is necessary to take into account the developmental features of the child characteristic of this period: speech, abstract thinking, perception, auditory and visual memory begin to form. When teaching younger students speech skills, teachers should adhere to a moderate regimen of physical activity, taking into account the weakness of the physiological apparatus of students. [12]

At this age, the nervous system of children continues to develop, various functions of the brain improve, the weight of the brain reaches the weight of an adult brain. Intensive development of the nervous system leads to a change in the balance between excitation and inhibition. If the process of speech development of a younger student takes place in the conditions of an educational and creative team, then the student quickly develops memory, speech, moral qualities and positive character traits. [6]

Pupils of primary school age grasp on the fly everything they hear and see. Teachers use special methods to train and reinforce the topic (keeping silence in the classroom, while listening to music). The topic studied using children's songs helps students remember 83% of the material, and 17% remain in their memory partially. Most children's songs are based on the effect of repetition, and thanks to this, speech, memory and perception develop better in children of primary school age. Many children's songs contain teaching, educational, instructive, patriotic aspects that are easier for children to digest. Children who study school subjects with music as the main teaching method have a sensitive and tender soul,

receptive to emotional impact. A powerful means of educating musically gifted children is the very valuable subject of education: classical music, represented in the curriculum by masterpieces of famous composers: Shostakovich, Glinka, Fauré, Tchaikovsky, Mozart, Beethoven and others. This music is able to deeply influence the soul of students, developing and elevating their consciousness, intellect and speech. [7]

Analyzing the results obtained, scientists put forward the following assumptions regarding the age characteristics of children of primary school age when using children's songs in the development of their speech:

- junior school age - a period of absorption, assimilation, accumulation of knowledge. This is the period of childhood most favorable for the development of speech influences;

- the teacher should know the age characteristics of children, but the approach to each child should be individual. A sensitive teacher, using an individual approach, is able to influence the development of all parameters in children;

- a differentiated approach to speech activity involves the teacher's involvement in the speech of each child, regardless of his age characteristics, type of temperament, knowledge, skills, abilities. [7]

We see the expediency of consistent work with students to develop their speech, creative thinking abilities, expand their erudition and horizons, and acquire their initial pedagogical skills with the help of children's songs. Acquaintance with the elements of songs can be very useful in the initial period of education, since in the end it can become an additional incentive to optimize the professional development of the speech component. Collective aesthetic work develops speech, auditory, visual memory, makes each student spiritually richer, and the educational process is significantly increased. [9].

Speech development skills are developed and improved at this stage of training, reaching a higher professional level and improving through more complex musical material. This is a new step in mastering the art of speech.

Thus, taking into account all of the above, we can conclude that an important task of teachers is to take care of the development of students' speech skills, which is facilitated by the study of the characteristics of the psychological development of children, based on the principles of its periodization. At primary school age, which is critical and responsible for beginning schoolchildren, it is necessary to develop literate speech, which is feasible with the help of children's songs.

In order to successfully complete the speech training cycle in the initial periods, it is necessary to take into account age characteristics at all stages and choose the right integration of songs correctly. In the educational and aesthetic activities of the class, when students perform songs, a system of speech values is organically formed, thanks to which the motivation for the development and self-improvement of speech is maintained. Having passed all the stages of speech training, schoolchildren are capable of independent interpretation of complex works, which indicates their full professional and personal development. We see the study of approaches to the development of speech of younger schoolchildren with song material as a promising direction for future scientific research.

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